

HOW ORGANIZATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AFFECTS SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF STAKEHOLDER THEORY

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Abstract

Given that corporate social responsibility (CSR) has been affected by various factors within or outside the organization, this study focuses on the interaction of CSR with various environmental dynamics. In Turkish literature, however, this interaction has not been studied comprehensively while organizations' CSR relationships, especially with their external environment, have remained uncertain. The study first aims to reveal the magnitude of the problem in Turkish literature related to CSR/CSR-environment interactions by reviewing the literature. Second, it seeks possible remedies for overcoming this problem by examining organizations' relations, especially with their external environment within the scope of stakeholder theory. To achieve these aims, the study firstly provides a systematic literature review (SLR) based on the Ulakbim Social Sciences Database after some discussion about CSR-organizational environment-stakeholder relationships. This relationship landscape is then examined within the context of stakeholder theory through a traditional review of the international literature. From this analysis, a conceptual framework is proposed to explain these relationships. Finally, some suggestions are presented for future studies.

Keywords: Social Responsibility, Corporate Social Responsibility, Organizational Environment, Stakeholders, Stakeholder Theory.

Jel Codes: M0, M1, M10, M14

Introduction

An organization is an entity in constant relation with its environment. The environment in which the organization operates and its relations with this environment is an important point to consider firstly. The organizations are subject to different institutional environments depending on their different contexts.

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Therefore, an important area for discussion concerns which aspects of the environment should be defined by which features, and which methods are more valid. As one of the cases where the impact of the organizational environment on organizational decisions and actions is felt most frequently, CSR is addressed in the literature within the framework of different organizational theories. Each theoretical perspective offers a different lens for understanding the relationship between environment and social responsibility. Since the definition of the environment largely determines the approach taken to the organization-environment relationship, it is useful to examine the environmental explanations of different organizational theories in the first place before going into the details of these relations. Therefore, the current study mainly relies on stakeholder theory to explain the underlying reasons for the diversity of CSR orientations among organizations, but also draws on different organizational theories to help define and embody the environment in which organizations operate. Stakeholders as members of this environment, they have the power to translate distal forces into reality (Lee, 2011). According to Campbell (2007), stakeholders, especially community groups, customers, and governments, force firms to behave in socially responsible ways. Organizational outcomes result from the interaction between stakeholders and the institutional environment (Fuenfschilling and Truffer, 2014; Thornton and Ocasio, 2008).

Despite comprehensive definitions in the literature, CSR is still considered hard to define fully (Jamali and Hossary, 2019). Furthermore, in spite of the increasing interest in the international literature on CSR-environment relations, the Turkish literature on this interaction is underdeveloped. As emphasized by several studies (Jamali and Hossary, 2019; Jamali, Karam, Yin and Soundararajan, 2017a), CSR has remained dominated by western-centric norms presented in the business and management CSR literature. For instance, whereas the developed world is characterized by well-developed governance systems, the developing world has diverse or contradictory systems that lead to a large variety of CSR orientations (Jamali and Hossary, 2019). From their review of 285 journal articles, Jamali and Karam (2016) discovered nuanced peculiarities relating to institutional stakeholders in enhancing the understandings of CSR in developing world, and more nuanced precursors than those found in the general CSR literature. This is thus a valuable topic requiring careful consideration. Moreover, the literature draws attention to this significant gap by constantly emphasizing the lack of research into the practice of CSR in developing countries (Jamali, Lund-Thomsen and Jeppesen 2017b; Jamali et al., 2017a; Jamali and Karam, 2016), although the number of studies exploring and supporting the different manifestations of CSR in developing country contexts has recently increased (Jamali et al., 2017a; 2017b). Given that Turkey is also a developing country, its unique experience of CSR can shed light on this important issue.

Therefore, the first aim of the current study is to reveal the magnitude of this problem by mapping the literature and determining the reasons for this situation. The second aim is to seek possible remedies by examining the relationships of Turkish organizations within the scope of stakeholder theory, specifically with their

external environment. This approach will contribute to understanding how the environment interacts with CSR while also aligning the Turkish national literature with its international counterpart.

To achieve these aims, this paper first introduces CSR, organizational environment, and stakeholder theory before discussing Turkish adoption of CSR in an institutional and historical context. This is followed by a systematic literature review (SLR) of the Ulakbim Social Sciences Database assess the national literature. The scope of this research area and the level of proficiency are determined based on CSR in general and CSR-environment interactions in particular. Drawing on these SLR results, the stakeholders affecting the CSR activities within the organization's environment are then discussed in detail in the context of stakeholder theory. A traditional literature review of international literature is used to guide the investigation of CSR-environment interactions in Turkish literature. Finally, a conceptual framework is presented to explain the relationships revealed by the preceding discussion. Thus, the current study provides both a fruitful comparison with the international literature and a conceptual assessment to raise awareness. This study will assist researchers wanting to investigate this issue and practitioners wanting to give direction to their organizations.

The Concept of CSR

The CSR concept has evolved significantly since it emerged in the 1950s. Especially after the 1970s, CSR definitions progressed towards including stakeholders as a crucial element of this environment, specifically organizations' responses to their expectations, interests, pressures, demands, etc. (Rahman, 2011; Arena, Azzone and Mapelli, 2018). As Carroll (1991, p. 43) notes, "There is a natural fit between the idea of corporate social responsibility and an organization's stakeholders". Also, according to Freeman and Velamuri (2006) "the main goal of CSR is to create value for key stakeholders and fulfill our responsibilities to them".

In recent years, diverse organizations in different environments and /sectors have increasingly turned towards social responsibility activities as an approach to doing business. Today, it is seen as a mainstream business element (Economist, 2008). The core idea of corporate social responsibility is that organizations must function beyond their direct economic interests. This creates a challenge for organizations trying to fulfill their obligations through a sensitive balance in their relationships with the environment; that is, by considering both social and commercial interests. Perhaps the most complex contexts for such balance are countries like Turkey, where there are many rapidly changing environmental factors. The literature also indicates that the term CSR in developing countries has an idiosyncratic meaning and although CSR in such contexts increasingly recognized to have some distinctive features, there is still a gap concerning this topic (Jamali and Neville, 2011; Jamali et al., 2017b). It is therefore important to discover the tendencies of organizations operating in environments where different, sometimes even contradictory organizational dialectics occur simultaneously. The impact of the environment and also its elements must be particularly taken into

consideration in building and maintaining social responsibility where organizations must find the optimum balance in their relationships with the environment.

Today, despite the complexity of the CSR definition (Sheey, 2015), we have a broadly accepted definition of CSR. According to the World Business Council for Sustainable Development, CSR is a continuing commitment to economic, social, and environmental development through engaging with multiple stakeholders (WBCSD, 2002). The European Commission offers a similar definition, highlighting social-environmental aspects and stakeholders (Commission of the European Communities, 2002). Given these definitions, Jamali and Hossary (2019) claim that successful CSR practices focus on business actions containing some form of stakeholder dialogue. That is, the core idea of CSR is that corporations have to respond to the expectations of various stakeholders (Jamali and Mirshak, 2007) in a complex, multi-faceted relationship (Greenwood, 2007). Because, CSR has become a business imperative (Waddock, Bodwell and Graves, 2002). In the same way, Aguinis (2011) by emphasizing this multidimensional nature of the CSR concept, defines it as “context-specific organizational actions and policies that take into account stakeholders’ expectations and the triple bottom line of economic, social, and environmental performance”.

However, despite the existence of a broadly accepted definition of CSR, in the literature CSR is divided into many components by many studies. These include terms such as sustainability, corporate responsibility, ethics, and corporate citizenship, stakeholder management, etc. (Freeman and Hasnaoui, 2011; Fassin, Van Rossem and Buelens, 2011). As stated by Freeman and Hasnaoui (2011), although these terms are used as synonyms by many, many others argue their differences as well. While some of the discussions consider corporate sustainability as a subset of CSR, some of them regard CSR as a subset of ethics (Freeman and Hasnaoui, 2011). For instance, according to the findings of Fassin, Van Rossem and Buelens’s study (2011), CSR and sustainability are seen closely related especially in the eyes of small-business owners. Sustainability is perceived as more practical-formal and less voluntary than CSR. On the other hand, some authors express the CSR practices performed by SMEs as ‘Silent CSR’ Jenkins (2004) or “Sunken CSR” (Perrini, 2006) that is more spontaneous, philanthropic and altruistic in nature. Furthermore, the CSR of SMEs in developing countries is characterized “as anchored in a blend of personal and religious motivations” (Jamali, Zanhour and Keshishian, 2009). Thus, in countries like Turkey that is rich in small-medium sized enterprises (SMEs), contribution to a better understanding of CSR meaning is also quite valuable in terms of exploring valid CSR dynamics in such developing country contexts.

Organizational Environment from Different Theoretical Lenses

The organizational environment is defined from various angles based on different theoretical perspectives. It is, therefore, useful to clarify the concept of the environment theoretically to develop a better understanding. For instance, while contingency theory suggests that the organization interacts with a more technical and economic environment, resource dependency theory sees the environment as a

battlefield where organizations engage in resource struggles with each other (Lawrence and Lorsh, 1967; Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978). In the latter case, an organization's survival directly depends on the power they have over other organizations (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978). In contrast, organizational ecology theory considers the environment as an economic milieu of organizations competing for similar resources to produce similar products. Since this environment includes many factors beyond the control of organizations, they cannot even think about intervening (Hannan and Freeman, 1977). Institutional theory meanwhile treats the environment more sociologically. The environment is not just economic – directing organizations to work efficiently and effectively – but also a legal, social, and cultural. Consequently, each organization has to legitimize its existence and activities (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). For macro-institutional theory, based on the basic assumptions of new institutional theory, the level of analysis is no longer the organizational field but the nation-state level. In explaining the formation of organizational forms in specific countries, macro-institutional theory emphasizes the role of that country's main institutions, such as the state, financial and education systems, and even cultural and religious beliefs (Whitley, 1992).

CSR is one of the cases where the impact of the organizational environment on organizational decisions and actions is felt most frequently and also addressed often in the international literature within the framework of these different theories discussed above. Since the way the definition of the environment defines the approaches to the organization-environment relationship to a large extent, each theory perspective offers a different lens for understanding relationship between environment and social responsibility. For instance, in contingency theory, rather than affecting the environment, organizations are expected to adapt to the environment, while in resource dependency theory, organizations are not only satisfied with adaptation, but also affect the environment to access the resources. In contrast, new institutional theory deals with the organization-environment relationship through a mutual interaction approach. That is, organizations are both shaped by the institutional environment within which they were established and reproduce or change the environment through their own actions and interactions with other organizations (Sargut and Özen 2015).

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory, which originated with Freeman (1984), focuses on a crucial component of business environment relationships (Strand and Freeman, 2015). According to Freeman (1984), stakeholders are defined as “any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the firm's objectives” (Strand and Freeman, 2015). It implies a shift from traditional bilateral relationships to multilateral relationships between the organization and environment (Martínez, Fernández and Fernández, 2016) with the organization is at the center of a nexus of relationships among stakeholders (Bridoux and Stoelhorst, 2014) such as “suppliers, owners, governments, customers, local community organizations, and employees” (Strand and Freeman, 2015).

Stakeholder theory is one of the most widely-used theoretical frameworks for evaluating CSR (Cantrell, Kyriazis, and Noble, 2015). Social responsibility is an important component in an organization's adjustment to its environment and stakeholders. (Martínez, Fernández and Fernández, 2016). Within CSR, the theory emphasizes the decisive role of actors in the organizational environment and acknowledges that there are many legitimate stakeholders in a series of interrelated relationships: the organization, consumers, suppliers, employees, and shareholders; the state, local community, environmentalists, competitors, and even the media (Freeman et al., 2010). Thus, a socially responsible firm has to both pay attention to all these stakeholders' interests while also balancing this multiplicity in its organizational decisions and actions (Garriga and Mele, 2004). These interests manifest themselves through various stakeholder pressures defined as "the ability and capacity of stakeholders to affect an organization by influencing its organizational decisions" (Helmig, Spraul and Ingenhoff, 2013:154). Because CSR orientations are largely affected by these pressures from multiple stakeholders, organizations need to know to whom are they responsible (Brown and Forster, 2013) and understand their stakeholders' concerns (Freeman and Velamuri, 2006). Through a stakeholder approach, organizations can manage these relationships with their external environment more effectively (Cantrell, Kyriazis, and Noble, 2015; Freeman and Velamuri, 2006).

Interrelationships among CSR, Organizational Environment, Stakeholders

CSR is a 'dynamic process' that observes the relationships arising from continuous communication between the organization and the stakeholders within the environment in which the firm operates (Kakabadse, Rozuel and Lee-Davies, 2005). According to Novethic (2003), firms need to consider all stakeholders while conducting their CSR activities (Kakabadse et al., 2005) because these activities comprise the triple bottom line triangle (economic, environmental, social) that result from their continuous relationship with stakeholders. According to Jones' CSR definition (1980, pp. 59-60), stakeholders are positioned at the center of CSR (Jones, Wicks and Freeman, 2002). However, the stakeholder concept has not grown with the CSR concept although two concepts are related to each other (Kakabadse et al., 2005).

Firms are surrounded by various institutional environments and stakeholders (Yang and Rivers, 2009). For example), organizational environments consist of various organizational groups, such as professions, associations, regulatory bodies, communities, or interest groups (Scott and Strang, 1987), or members of groups such as customers, communities, shareholders, etc. (Jones et al., 2002). Organizational environments are thus filled with multiple and even conflicting stakeholder pressures that create 'incompatible prescriptions' for organizations (Greenwood et al., 2011).

According to Lee (2011, p.287), these stakeholders "can serve their own interests by directly pressuring firms" and "also diminish the effect by acting as buffers". In such complex environments filled with multiple logics, some forces

will be more effective than others because some stakeholders may promote their logics more effectively than others (Lee, 2011). Although the stakeholders are embedded in the organizational environment, organizational decisions and outcomes are influenced by the interaction between them (Thornton and Ocasio, 2008). It is therefore important to discover the tendencies of organizations operating in environments like Turkey, with varied, even contradictory organizational dialectics.

CSR Phenomenon in Turkey

Turkey is politically, socially, and culturally complex, diverse, and unique, which is also reflected in its national business systems. Given the significant gap in the literature deriving from the lack of research into the practice of CSR in developing countries (see Jamali and Karam, 2018; Jamali and Carroll, 2017), the impact of Turkey's national context on CSR practices should thus be evaluated in detail. As stated by Jamali (2014), CSR practices can not be separated from the context, especially in developing countries where the unique characteristics and the peculiar CSR expressions have. Even more, Jamali et al. (2017b) emphasize that SMEs in developing countries exhibit different CSR orientations and their practices "often differ from what is commonly encountered in industrialized countries". The term of CSR and its meaning is stated largely as meaningless to SMEs (Roberts, Lawson and Nicholls, 2006). Because the CSR debate is heavily driven by a western-centric view. As such, in recent years, the calls for more research on developing country SMEs particularly within the context of CSR seem to have increased (Jamali et al., 2009). Given that SMEs make up 99.8% of the registered business in Turkey (European Training Foundation, 2018), it provides a favorable context to examine such issues. In this context, it is expected to shed light on unexplored power dynamics surrounding CSR.

CSR development in Turkey began from the concept of philanthropy, which is a legacy of the Ottoman period. With the establishment of the Republic of Turkey, the central state came to the forefront. After industrialization began in the 1950s, and especially during the 1970s with a stronger private sector and external influences, the understanding of philanthropy continued to develop, partly for legitimacy and partly due to traditional factors (Türker, 2015). CSR was also affected by post-1980 liberalization movements and the impact of multinational companies in the post-1990s. During the 2000s, the business system, and CSR specifically, have been mainly influenced by the Justice and Development Party's economic and liberalization policies (Türker, 2015; Alakavuklar et al., 2009). The type of CSR that emerged during the 1970s' adaptation period, seeing philanthropy as an important branch of organization's socially responsible activities, remains widely accepted in Turkey (Ararat, 2004). It particularly reflects Turkey's predominantly Islamic perspective (Türker, 2016). The interaction of these traditional approaches with contemporary economic, political, and social factors creates unique characteristics in Turkey as a developing country. It is therefore important to analyse these features to understand how CSR practices have evolved. As Jamali et al. (2017b) points out, the relationship between environment,

organization, and CSR in developing countries has distinct interaction dynamics. Yet, the CSR literature still focuses more on multinational companies rather than small-medium sized enterprises while offering little research of developing country contexts (Karam and Jamali, 2017).

As mentioned before, the role of actors is also a very important factor in CSR, especially when the organization's environment is highly complex, with sometimes contradictory institutional logics, as in the case of Turkey (Türker and Altuntas, 2017). Previous CSR research has revealed the importance of such assessments of the different dynamics in developing country contexts (Jamali et al., 2017a; 2017b; Jamali and Karam, 2016) and also the impact of actors (Rodríguez Bolívar, Garde Sánchez and López Hernández, 2015; Jamali et al., 2017b). Therefore, analysing the organization-environment interaction, and actors' decisions, choices, and actions should be carefully considered. In this respect, the literature shows that the impact of personal touch in CSR is more vivid in SMEs and family-owned firms (see Jamali et al., 2017b; Jamali and Neville, 2011; Jenkins, 2006). Their CSR activities are often portrayed as driven by owner-managers' personal preferences, beliefs or attitudes (Jamali et al., 2009). Given the fact that SMEs represents 99,8% of all registered entities (European Training Foundation, 2018) and approximately 95% of them are family businesses (Erdem and Erdem, 2011), Turkey also offers a unique opportunity to observe and reveals the underlying dynamics of such a personalized approach to CSR.

The following section reports on the SLR conducted to assess CSR itself and CSR-organizational environment interactions in the Turkish literature to reveal as the issues mentioned above.

Methodology

In line with the purpose and scope of this study, an SLR was conducted to assess the existing knowledge about CSR in Turkey within the context of CSR-environment interactions. SLR is an important way to review a large and complex research literature in a specific area in a transparent, replicable, and rigorous manner while at the same time providing synthesis (Victor, 2008). Because SLR provides a strict protocol for the literature review and evaluation (Boell and Cecez-Kecmanovic, 2015). It is the most suitable tool for achieving the aims of this study. The study tries contributes to the literature by offering the first integrative study of Turkey's CSR literature and maps out the field's development while presenting replicable content for future studies to draw on.

The Ulakbim Social Sciences DataBase was used for the SLR as it is a suitable and valuable data source for the national literature within the scope of the current study. The review was conducted on articles published between 2013 and 2018, identified using a keyword search for 'CSR' in keywords, titles, and abstracts. The keyword search was carried out only for 'CSR', because using some other keywords (and/or) together with 'CSR' did not work. On the other hand, the keyword search for 'CSR' in keywords, titles, and abstracts was conducted separately due to the lack of an inclusive criterion such as 'topic' on search options.

While the search in keywords did not give any results, search in titles and abstracts gave 61 and 133 results respectively. After removing 56 repetitive articles within a total of 194 articles, it was performed other filtering steps. Firstly, within the scope of the preliminary filtering, 20 articles in a foreign language were excluded from the list. In doing so, 118 articles obtained. Secondly, 118 articles were ranked according to the citation reports. Finally, the whole list was examined respectively according to the strings reflect the study's focus, i.e, the primary concepts that the review examines CSR, stakeholders, stakeholder, organizational environment, etc. After excluding the articles that failed to satisfy the study inclusion criteria, the first 35 articles that are more related to the topic of the current study were included in the final list. Table 1 presents the studies in terms of research type, research area, theoretical base, level of analysis, and main variables. 35

Findings

The selected studies were evaluated according to the features highlighted in Table 1's main headings (type of study, field of study, theoretical base, level of analysis, main variables).

Regarding research methods, 29 studies used only one quantitative (survey or panel data analysis, or secondary data analysis) or qualitative methods (interview, content analysis, case study, field research, or discourse analysis). Only two studies (study (S.) 8 and 18) used multiple research methods.

Regarding study field, the most frequent was management (23 studies), followed by marketing (6 studies), accounting-finance (5 studies), and sociology (1 study).

Regarding theoretical approach, only four studies drew on a specific theoretical approach (S.4 [Institutional Theory]; S.10 [Cultural Theory]; S.11 [Marxist Theory]; S.24 [Action Theory]).

Regarding level of analysis, 24 studies examined the issue at the organizational level while 11 examined the subject at the individual level. Most individual-level studies were in marketing (S.20, 25, 33, 35). Only study (S.22) combined both levels.

Regarding variables, CSR was the most frequent independent variable, although it was operationalized in various ways, such as CSR reporting, activities, applications, policies, strategies, perceptions, and discourses. For studies that included demographic variables as independent variables (S.1-9-12-27), the effects of these variables on CSR perceptions were investigated by three studies, which included public relations (S.6), board diversity (S.8), and national culture (S.10) as independent variables. Only one study (S.33) included the independent variable 'social purpose-linked marketing campaign'.

CSR was also the most frequent dependent variable, operationalized in various forms, such as CSR practices, perception, and discourse. The second-most common dependent variable was financial performance (S.214, 26, 29). Eight other

studies included other dependent variables: corporate identity (S.4), consumer purchasing behaviour (S.5), organizational benefit (S.13), firm characteristics (S.18), customer engagement (S.22), brand awareness (S.25), employee job satisfaction (S.30), and consumer perception (S.35).

Within the context of distinct CSR-related relationships (as seen Table1), three studies (S.4, 5, 8) examined, respectively, the moderator effects of actors, cultural context, and institutional environment variables on family businesses.

Qualitative studies, or studies that did not assess the specific quantitative relationships between dependent and independent variables, mostly examined CSR discourses, awareness levels, reporting and implementation differences between organizations (S.7, 11, 15, 16, 17, 23). CSR perception was the second most common (S.1, 24). Finally, some studies examined CSR in terms of various dimensions (S.19, 20, 28, 32)

Regarding the studies' results, CSR perceptions were not consistently affected by demographic factors; however, CSR practices had a positive effect on organizational attitudes.

For the relationship between CSR reporting and financial performance, two studies found no significant relationship (S.2, 14) while one study found a weak negative relationship (S.29) and another study (S.26) reported a positive relationship for some financial indicators.

Three studies (S.3, 4, 13) that CSR policies and practices encourage organizations' institutional transformation and identity acquisition.

Three studies demonstrated the importance of the cultural and institutional context for CSR practices (S.4, 8, 10) while one study (S.4) highlighted the role of actors in this relationship (.

Studies focusing on marketing showed that CSR practices improve consumer behavior and perceptions (S.5-35), customer loyalty (S.22), and brand awareness.

In all the reviewed studies, CSR was analyzed in terms of simple linear relations from a limited perspective that was practice- rather than theory-oriented, using cross-sectional research designs, rather than process-based approaches that incorporate the effects of different environmental dynamics or environmental contexts. In addition, the methods used were generally not presented clearly. From examining the CSR literature in Turkey, Yamak (2007) emphasizes the lack of approaches based on historical and contextual processes. This points to the dilemma of 'Ceremonial Empiricism' – the unquestioning adoption of the dominant empiricist paradigm in a field, which generates a monotonous, inadequate literature (Özen, 2002). Thus far, the Turkish literature had not yet steered researchers and practitioners in this field in the right direction regarding the need to understand the context of CSR in general and CSR-environment relations specifically.

The SLR results clearly reveal that the Turkish CSR literature has so far largely ignored the important relationships and theoretical links mentioned earlier in this section. In particular, researchers have ignored the important mediating role of stakeholders in this relationship, the unique characteristics of developing country contexts (distinct CSR adaptation and implementation processes), and the important role of actors as change agents.

Given these SLR results, this paper now focuses on these ignored multiple and complex, stakeholder-mediated relationships in CSR/CSR-organizational environment interactions by reviewing the international CSR literature. A traditional literature review method is applied to previous studies, mostly indexed in the Web of Science database. The aim is to bring Turkey's national CSR-related literature closer to the international literature by supporting the dissemination of knowledge of CSR studies in other contexts.

Table1: Ulakbim Social Science Database SLR Results

S.N.	Study	Research Type*	Field	Theory	Analysis Level	Independent Variable	Moderator/Mediator Variables	Dependent Variable
1	Koçoğlu and Aksoy, 2017	Quantitative (Survey)	Management	-	Individual	Demographic Variables	-	CSR Perception
2	Kaya and Yazan, 2017	Quantitative (Panel Data Analysis)	Accounting-Finance	-	Organization	CSR Reporting	-	Financial Performance
3	Öktem et al., 2015	Quantitative (Field Study)	Management	-	Organization	CSR Policies	-	CSR Practices
4	Duman and Aksak, 2017	Qualitative (Case Study)	Management	Institutional Theory	Organization	CSR Policies	Role of Actor in Family Business	Corporate Identity
5	Astarhoğlu, 2017	Quantitative (Survey)	Marketing	-	Organization	CSR Practices	Cultural Context	Consumer Purchasing Behaviour
6	Peltekoğlu and Tozlu, 2017	Quantitative (Descriptive Statistics)	Management	-	Organization	Public Relations	-	CSR
7	Şentürk and Fidan, 2017	Qualitative (Case Study)	Management	-	Organization	Collaboration and Participation in CSR		
8	Tarhan et al., 2016	Quantitative (Secondary Data Analysis) + Qualitative (Content Analysis)	Management	-	Organization	Board Diversity	Institutional Environment	CSR Discourses of Organizations
9	Serinkli, 2016	Quantitative (Survey)	Management	-	Individual	Demographic Variables	-	CSR Perception
10	Koparan et al., 2016	Quantitative (Secondary Research Analysis)	Management	Cultural Theory	Organization	National Culture	-	CSR
11	Akbas and Topal, 2016	Conceptual	Sociology	Marxist	Organization	CSR Discourses of Organizations		

12	Yurttadur et al., 2016	Quantitative (Survey)	Management	-	Individual	Demographic Variables	-	CSR Perception
13	Öztürk and Öktem, 2016	Quantitative (Survey)	Management	-	Organization	CSR Reporting	-	Organizational Benefit
14	Celik et al., , 2016	Quantitative (Panel Data Analysis)	Accounting-Finance	-	Organization	CSR Reporting	-	Financial Performance
15	Öztürk, 2016	Qualitative (Content Analysis)	Management	-	Organization	Disclosures in Sections on Environmental Reporting in CSR Reports		
16	Parlakkaya et al, 2016	Qualitative (Field Research)	Management	-	Organization	CSR Practices and Reporting Differences		
17	Akmese and Aras, 2016	Qualitative (Field Research)	Management	-	Organization	CSR Practices and Reporting Differences		
18	Yıldız et al., 2016	Qualitative (Content Analysis) + Quantitative (Panel Data Analysis)	Accounting-Finance	-	Organization	Disclosures in Sections on Environmental Reporting in CSR Reports	-	Firm Characteristics
19	Güven, 2016	Conceptual	Management	-	Organization	To reveal the relationship between the CSR concept and ethics and to determine the importance of these activities in the process of corporate communication		
20	Şüküroğlu, 2016	Conceptual	Marketing	-	Organization	Consumption Culture, Consumer Society, Citizenship and Corporate SR Concepts are discussed and the relations between them are examined.		
21	Torun, 2016	Qualitative (Case Study)	Management	-	Organization	CSR strategies, responsibilities and practices of Danish Parliament on CSR axis and the effects of all these on CSR are examined.		
22	Aydın and Erdogan, 2016	Quantitative (Survey)	Marketing	-	Individual-Organization	CSR Practices	-	Customer Loyalty
23	Bat, 2016	Qualitative (Case Study)	Management	-	Organization	Differences in CSR Practices		
24	Hostut, 2015	Qualitative (Discourse Analysis)	Management	Action Theory	Organization	It has been tried to clarify how CSR reports are evaluated as understandable and reliable reports by different stakeholder groups		

25	Denecli, 2015	Quantitative (Survey)	Marketing	-	Individual	CSR Practices	-	Brand Awareness
26	Dastan and Bellikli, 2015	Quantitative (Secondary Data Analysis)	Accounting-Finance	-	Organization	CSR Practices	-	Financial Performance
27	Demir and Türkmen, 2015	Quantitative (Survey)	Management	-	Individual	Demographic Variables	-	CSR Perception
28	Buyukyılmaz and Fidan, 2015	Conceptual	Management	-	Organization	CSR is examined within the scope of definition, SR theories, reasons for directing enterprises to SR activities and SR areas.		
29	Basar, 2014	Quantitative (Descriptive Statistics)	Accounting-Finance	-	Organization	CSR Practices	-	Financial Performance
30	Avcı and Akdemir, 2014	Quantitative (Field Research and Survey)	Management	-	Individual	CSR Perception	-	Employee Satisfaction
31	Öksüz, 2014	Qualitative (Interview)	Management	-	Individual	Relationship Between Public Relations and CSR		
32	Engin and Akgöz, 2013	Conceptual	Management	-	Organization	To examine the relationship between the concepts of sustainable development, corporate sustainability and CSR in a theoretical framework and to make a general evaluation on concepts		
33	Çakır Özdemir, 2013	Quantitative (Survey)	Marketing	-	Individual	Social purpose-linked marketing campaigns	-	CSR Perception
34	Morçin, 2013	Quantitative (Survey)	Management	-	Individual	Employees' CSR Perception		
35	Onaran et al., 2013	Quantitative (Survey)	Marketing	-	Individual	CSR Practices	-	CSR Perception

*As the methods applied in some studies were unclear, both the authors' own explanations and the classifications of that study's authors are included when grouping the "research type"

How do Stakeholders Affect CSR Orientation?

The organizational environments within which organizations carry out daily operations and which directly affect their performance include competitors, suppliers, customers, and the labour market (Daft, 2010). This environmental layer forms the basis for stakeholder management as companies interact with key stakeholders, such as customers, investors, suppliers, and competitors, within this layer. The pressures exerted by these stakeholders are an important premise of CSR (Yu and Choi, 2016). Regarding the environment-organization-CSR relationship, some of the theories discussed above can provide an explanatory framework for the various roles of these actors. For example, actors with manipulative (resource dependency theory) or interactive roles (institutional theory) may affect the process in terms of the top-level authority for organizational decisions and orientations. One of the most studied subjects in the CSR literature is the interactions and impact of stakeholders on organizations (Park and Ghauri, 2015; Maon et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2015; Cheng, Ioannou and Serafeim, 2014). This is because organizations' survival and success depend on their ability to create value and satisfaction for these stakeholders. Consequently, they should take into account various stakeholder concerns when making strategic decisions. Stakeholder theory describes organizations as located in a series of interrelated relationships in which the state, consumers, competitors, local community, and media are seen as legitimate stakeholders (Vashchenko, 2017). CSR decisions thus need to reflect the demands of stakeholders and achieve common strategic goals with them (Freeman et al., 2010). These different dynamics from organizations' interactions with stakeholders in their environment affect CSR formation and development. At the same time, they shape the quantity and quality of the value produced by CSR activities. This implies that an organization working to achieve its goals needs to determine which stakeholders, in terms of CSR, affect the organization, how, and in what direction.

The next section examines various stakeholders highlighted in the international literature regarding their interaction with CSR to develop a better understanding of their key impacts on these issues. This approach will also provide an opportunity to compare the Turkish and international literatures. Additionally, based on this review, Figure 1. presents various stakeholder groups on the organizational environment. It shows the influence of different stakeholders on an organization's CSR orientation, manifested through their distinct expectations, demands, interests, and pressures.

Competitors

Competitors are one of the most CSR prominent stakeholders. Companies may implement CSR programs in response to customer demands to retain existing customers, attract new ones, distinguish themselves from their competitors, and create a sustainable competitive advantage (Kiessling, Isaksson and Yaşar, 2016; Porter and Kramer, 2006). However, the literature gives inconsistent results regarding the impact of competition on CSR. While some studies conclude it has a positive impact (Sanchez-Hernandez et al., 2016; Flammer, 2015; Ramchander, Schwebach and Staking, 2012), others report an opposite effect (Campbell, 2007; Meng et al., 2016).

Regarding the positive impact of competition on CSR, Becker-Olsen, Cudmore and Hill (2006) reported that 52% of consumers boycott organizations that do not participate in CSR activities if other relevant firms implement CSR. The CSR orientation of organizations is increasingly influenced by the CSR practices of competitors. Although organizations define their own CSR activities, they tend to protect their position in the market by examining their competitors' practices (Park and Ghauri, 2015).

When key companies in an industry start implementing CSR principles, other players in the market can follow it because more successful competitors can be mimicked, especially under new and/or ambiguous conditions (Di Maggio and Powell, 1983). Various studies have examined such peer effects, in terms of the theory of mimetic isomorphism. They find that companies intentionally develop their own CSR strategies based on their competitors' approaches to protect their own market shares and to prevent future cash flow problems (Liu and Wu, 2016; Cao, Liang and Zhang, 2016).

Another significant influencer of CSR trends is the level of competition in an industry. For instance, Szutowski and Ratajczak (2016) used SLR to conduct a meta-analysis of academic articles from 22,000 journals. They concluded that strong competition explains the increasing importance of both innovation and CSR practices (Szutowski and Ratajczak, 2016). Firms can use CSR in competitive environments to decrease competition and increase market density in the long term. If consumers prefer goods that are produced in a socially responsible manner, companies can use CSR strategically to distribute their products and potentially reduce competition (Planer-Friedrich and Sahn, 2017).

Competition can also hinder the development of CSR if it is too strong or weak. In the former case, companies try to reduce the costs as much as possible as their profit margins are too low and the organization's survival is seriously at risk; in the latter case, the absence of competing organizations that could be used as benchmarks for market comparisons means that organizational reputation and customer loyalty may be ignored since they will be seen as factors that do not affect profitability and sales much (Campbell, 2007). Meng et al. (2016), for example, investigated 792 Chinese-registered manufacturing companies between 2006 and 2008. They found that both too much and too little industrial competition caused organizations to reduce their environmental responsibility.

Customers

Many studies have confirmed that a socially responsible company image plays an important role in customers' purchasing preferences. Well-known, socially recognized companies selling to the final consumers face the strongest pressures. In addition to being price and quality-oriented, customers are also interested in whether employers treats its employees or the environment in a socially responsible way (Kubenka ve Myskova, 2009). Managers generally know that employees, customers, and shareholders are sensitive to the organization's public image of the firm, so CSR activities help in shaping this image (Perez and Rodríguez-Del-

Bosque, 2015; Hasan et al., 2016). Thus, if consumers monitor the CSR activities of firms, managers will be more likely to behave in a socially responsible manner. For instance, Jiang et al. (2015) have shown that the customer responses given to the CSR strategy of the firms positively affect the relationship between managers' CSR mentality and selection of CSR strategy.

According to Campell (2007), stakeholder pressures force companies to act in a socially responsible way. Shareholder and government pressure have greater positive impacts on decisions than customers and competitors (Wang et al., 2015).

Turning to the negative effects of customer pressure on CSR practices. For instance, the power of social media enables customers to express their views on a specific company's CSR-related activities. This can provoke deeper reflection about the social consequences of these companies' behaviours (Porter and Kramer 2006). However, Khan, Ferguson and Perez 2(015) found that customer responses to SCR practices have been largely examined in the context of developed countries. Furthermore, it has made an important call for future studies, emphasizing that few studies have yet analyzed customer responses to CSR perceptions in developing countries.

Employees

Employees are quite prominent stakeholders that can significantly influence the CSR activities of the organizations (Park and Ghauri, 2015). Given that CSR is guided by the organization's employees, they affect the process from planning to implementation.

Organizations have various direct social responsibilities for their employees, such as human resources, wage and compensation policies, work environment, and elimination of child labour and forced labor.

Organizations can benefit if employees internalize basic corporate values that can feed into their performance. A strong culture can improve organizational performance by shaping and coordinating employee behavior. This shared understanding and collaboration plays a crucial role in implementing CSR-related strategies (Lee, Park and Lee, 2013). Wang et al. (2015) reported that working pressure had a negative impact on CSR. This interesting finding may reflect the high-power distance characteristic of Chinese culture, which enables administrators to take less notice of the views of the subordinates.

Stakeholder theory considers CSR in two dimensions: external and internal. The external dimension concerns the broad relationship between organizations and their communities while the internal dimension concerns employees. Like other stakeholders, employees demand some benefits such as economic, psychological etc. from their organizations (Sanchez-Hernandez et al., 2016). For instance, if employers provide challenging or satisfying jobs, they can provide functional benefits. Thus, employees will perceive a socially responsible employer as the main driver of internal socially responsible practices (Sanchez-Hernandez et al., 2016). Previous research on CSR focused more investigated customers' perceptions, leaving employees' views on CSR largely unresearched (Lee et al., 2013).

Shareholders

CSR is a multilevel structure, extending from a narrow concept focused on maximizing shareholder assets to broader actions related to higher social goods than the company's own interests (Lee et al., 2013). Companies are primarily motivated to maximize shareholder benefits through actions that increase operating profits. However, other stakeholders surrounding the company prefer to interact with organizations that work better on CSR (Park and Ghauri, 2015). Agency theory explains the various problems arising from the different interests of the principal-agent relationship between shareholders and managers. According to Dam and Scholtens (2013), for example, the interests of small and large shareholders may vary. Large shareholders, who have a greater influence, will have a greater impact on the company than minor shareholders due to stronger incentives and more effective monitoring activities. While Dam and Scholtens (2013) focused on the link between CSR and ownership concentration, they also included explanations about other studies showing that the relationship can occur in both directions (positively and/or negatively). Their study showed that ownership concentration has a negative effect on CSR. Given the balance between financial performance and social performance, the price paid for social performance will be higher for large shareholders. In other words, even if the social enterprise seems to be quite appropriate, the gains will not outweigh the shareholder's own costs. Thus, the greater the share of a shareholder in a company, the less likely that social enterprises will be preferred by this company. Shareholders may thus develop a CSR policy at the expense of their own financial gains. In such a case, other stakeholders will probably earn more than the stakeholders themselves (Dam and Scholtens, 2015).

Suppliers

Suppliers are important stakeholders that are limited to contracts with a company while being directly involved in the economic process. Although they are directly involved in CSR activities, they work in terms of sustainability rather than CSR (Türker and Altuntas, 2014). Two common practices in sustainable supply chain management include supplier assessment (supplier evaluation, selection, development, training, monitoring, risk evaluation) (Awaysheh and Klassen, 2010; Foerstl, Reuter, Hartmann and Blome, 2010; Reuter, Foerstl, Hartmann and Blome, 2010; Sarkis, 2012; Tachizawa, Thomsen, Montes-Sancho, 2012; Seuring and Müller, 2008), and supply base continuity (transparency, traceability, collaboration, information sharing, risk evaluation) (Golicic and Smith, 2013; Mollenkopf, Stolze, Tate and Ueltschy, 2010; Pagell and Wasserman, 2010; Carter and Rogers, 2008).

According to Freeman (1984), a socially responsible company should consider the expectations of suppliers that have significant impacts on organizational performance (Park and Ghauri, 2015). A good supplier that shows environmental awareness and environmental responsibility while carrying out its activities plays a major role in influencing businesses to protect the environment. Local suppliers can be particularly effective stakeholders due to their commitment to environmental protection practices and local responses (Ahmad et al., 2017). Local suppliers and many other groups can shape CSR concepts through their

expectations that firms will behave in socially responsible ways while conducting their operations (Bondy et al., 2012).

Discussion

As stated before, this study firstly mapped the literature to gain a better understanding of the reasons for problems in the Turkish literature regarding CSR and CSR-organizational environment interaction. The results indicate that the CSR concept is a very interesting subject, but the results of the in-depth evaluation reveal some problems in the national literature. Specifically, despite some Turkish studies investigating CSR with a process-oriented approach, the literature is dominated by practice-oriented research. This tendency has not allowed the subject to be examined in depth. Instead, research is trapped in a vicious circle within a limited framework focused on certain easily-measurable variables. In addition, few studies in the literature have a theoretical foundation. Consequently, the important relationships and theoretical links in the international literature have been largely ignored in the Turkish literature.

In addition, as a developing country, Turkey's unique contextual features and distinct transformation need to be examined by CSR researchers. Organizational environments comprise multiple and even conflicting institutional logics (Greenwood et al., 2011; Thornton and Ocasio, 2008). It is therefore very important to understand CSR-related processes like translation, adaptation, and implementation in countries like Turkey (Turker, 2015; Jamali et al., 2017a).

The Turkish CSR literature has tended to ignore the complex, multiple dynamics and processes comprising the CSR relationship between organizations and the environment. Additionally, the various effects of stakeholders on CSR issues in the context of multiple pressures have not been explored deeply. Therefore, the previous section of the study drew attention to these ignored relationships by reviewing the international literature in terms of stakeholder theory. In the light of this review, Figure 1. illustrates the impact of various stakeholder groups on organizations' CSR orientations. It shows that the organizations are subject to a range of pressures from its stakeholders while trying to perform their CSR activities. Therefore, different components of an organization's stakeholder environment can create various combinations and effects on CSR-related issues, so different stakeholders can have different impacts on the organization's CSR outcomes. Thus, to make CSR feasible, organizations need to clearly understand their stakeholder environment. Several stakeholder management techniques, such as stakeholder dialogue or stakeholder engagement, may be crucial for smoothing this challenging process. At this point, it may be also useful to address the issue from a theoretical viewpoint to resolve the inconsistencies between empirical studies carried out in different times and contexts, and with different methods. Contingency theory focuses on the harmony of the organization with the environment (Lawrence and Lorsh, 1967; Burns and Stalker, 1961; Emery and Trist, 1965; Thompson, 1961; Duncan, 1972). It suggests that the organization needs to change structural contingencies in a dynamic and uncertain environment. In contrast, resource dependency theory defines the environment as a battlefield where organizations struggle for resources.

Figure1. Stakeholders on the Organizational Environment

Stakeholder definitions are adapted from Thomson, Ocasio and Lounsbury (2012); Thomson, Jones and Kury (2005)

In response, organizations use a variety of manipulative strategies, such as horizontal integration with competitors or inter-organizational coordination strategies (diversification, entering new markets), to reduce the fierce competition to procure resources. Organizational ecology theory focuses on the long-term survival of organizations within their environments (Hannan and Freeman, 1977). The theory provides a density dependence mechanism to explain the birth and death rates of organizations. It then connects this to competition and legitimacy processes (Hannan and Freeman, 1977). Considering that CSR practices serve as both a competitive and legitimating tool, it can be expected that these processes can function similarly for organizations' CSR practices. In sum, If the organization thinks that it will contribute to its competitive conditions (Contingency), long-term survival (Organizational Ecology), facilitate its access to resources (Resource Dependency), legitimize its activities (institutional theory) and manage stakeholder relations more effectively (stakeholder theory), it will focus on CSR activities.

The review conducted here has shown that the international literature addresses the issue very differently to the local literature. Through this analysis, the present study has developed a conceptual framework to represent the most important actors within the organizational environment, and their multifaceted influences on CSR-related issues. The study has also highlighted the neglected

points in the national literature to help draw the national literature more in line with international CSR research.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Indrawing on a point made by Ağlargöz (2016), that the first step is to ask the right research questions, this study offers a number of suggestions for future studies to contribute to the development of the CSR literature towards the right direction and to support organizations practically. The study indicates that a paradigm shift is needed for evaluating the CSR-organizational environment interaction. The recommendations for CSR research in Turkey can be summarized as follows:

- CSR in Turkey should be examined in depth in terms of contextual features.
- More theoretically-integrated CRS studies are needed.
- Longitudinal studies are needed to examine the transformation of CSR practices in Turkey.
- For a sensitive area like CSR, multi-research methods are needed to clarify the topic.
- The collective impacts of SMEs and the role of managers as change agents should be analyzed in depth for developing countries in general and Turkey specifically.
- Given the considerable strength of family businesses in Turkey, it constitutes a specific context to analyze CSR practices.
- Organizations should develop a CSR strategy with stakeholder management activities; issues related to collaboration-engagement-partnerships are key to success.
- Research is needed regarding the competition effect, widely discussed in the international literature but neglected in Turkey.
- CSR should not be considered as a superficial phenomenon to analyze only from the contents of CSR reporting and institutional websites; rather, the focus should be on new data collection methods to gain more valid and reliable results.
- The multiplicity and complexity issues in the institutional environments, especially within developing country contexts, should rigorously examined.

Recalling the valuable suggestions made by Özen (2002, p.5), it is important for CSR to be studied by researchers who “know the meaning of scientific endeavour, the methodological and theoretical diversity in the field, the societal context where they are, and their social identity”. In this respect, by pointing out the gap in the Turkish literature regarding CSR and by emphasizing the important roles of stakeholders in CSR issues, especially in developing country contexts, it is hoped that this study can stimulate future research. Finally, it is hoped that the conceptual framework derived from this study can contribute to knowledge of the associations between the key constructs (organizational environment, stakeholders, and CSR) reviewed in this study.

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